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Are CEOs hedge against share price fall?

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Using a combination of Agency Theory, Institutional Theory and Signaling Theory, this study investigates the link between CEO characteristics and share price for a sample of 134 publicly traded firms from the Main Board of the Nigerian Exchange, for a period of fifteen (15) years (2008-2022). CEO characteristics considered are duality, nationality, gender, tenure, turnover and ownership. In contrast to prior literature, share price is defined as the average share price at the beginning and at the end of the year. Furthermore, the analysis examines the association between CEO characteristics and share price. Finally, the present study analyzes the relationship between CEO characteristics and share price conjointly. Comparable to general findings from studies using Nigerian data, the empirical analysis as a whole shows that CEO nationality, CEO gender and firm size are significant. However, CEO duality, tenure, turnover, ownership, leverage, listing age and firm growth are not significant with share price. Overall, results provide evidence that CEO roles in maximizing share price vary across firms and characteristics. Consequently, these findings do not lend support to the CEO duality, tenure, turnover, and ownership in maintaining corporate share price. Overall, our results indicate that maximizing share price depend on corporate CEO nationality, CEO gender and firm size.

Keywords: CEO characteristics, duality, gender, nationality, ownership, share price, tenure, turnover, leverage, firm listing age, firm size, firm growth

1. Introduction

We examine whether the characteristics of the CEO, which reflect its effectiveness, affect companies' share price. We also evaluate whether this relation depends on firm leverage, firm listing age, firm size, and firm growth. Our focus on these control variables is particularly important to explain that corporation's search for change agent stakeholders to maximize share price is not only affected by the change agent stakeholder but also by control variables.

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In the last few decades, companies' share price performance has received increased attention and concern, worldwide (Alam & Uddin, 2009; Al-Shawawreh, 2014; Anoruo & Mustafa, 2007; Asif et al., 2016; Capstaff et al., 2004; Chen et al., 2009; Donnelly & Sheehy, 1996; Omran & Pointon, 2004; Seguin & Smoller, 1997; Stoll & Whaley, 1997). This is because, a company's share price is the reflection of market value of investment, held by shareholders. In corporations, there are two (2) benefits to equity shareholders (1) dividend payments, if any (2) capital gains (appreciation), when the shares are disposed by the shareholders. These benefits have attracted investors considerably over time. However, research on the role of the CEO in shaping share price is still in its early stages. As clearly shown in the opening statement of this introduction, share price is now a relevant area of research, and there are still several opportunities to further investigate the nexus between the CEO characteristics and share price of firms. Understanding the aspect of the CEO leading to the improving share price and how they change in over time is important because such a decision may help to maximize the value of a firm, among other characteristics.

We use a large Nigerian sample to assess the characteristics of the CEO that determinant the share price of a firm in Nigeria. Specifically, we examine data from 134 listed firms for the period 2008–2022 and classify CEO characteristics into six types: (i) duality, (ii) nationality, (iii) gender, (iv) tenure, (v) turnover, and (vi) ownership. We argue that when the CEO displays higher effectiveness or performance, it ensures higher or improved company's share price. We predict that companies with high CEO effectiveness or financial performance have a higher probability of also having CEO that shares the following characteristics (i) duality, (ii) nationality, (iii) gender, (iv) tenure, (v) turnover, and (vi) ownership.

Our initial a priori expectation is that all of the attributes of the CEO that we consider as proxies for measuring CEO effectiveness are positively associated with share price. Our main results provide evidence that these attributes also determine the market value of share price: CEO nationality and CEO gender. Additionally, firms have a higher probability of choosing a CEO that is foreign and woman. Using the six CEO attributes provides further evidence that the effectiveness or financial performance of the CEO has direct impacts on the market value of share price. We also assess the bivariate interaction between the CEO characteristics on one hand and share price on the other hand using Pearson Correlation Analysis. Our results indicate that companies with CEO characteristics such as foreign and women, are more likely to maximize the market value of their share price.

This study makes three important contributions. First, we provide evidence that the link between CEO characteristics and share price is important, thus addressing an aspect matter that is largely ignored by scholars and is one of the shortcomings of signaling theory. This paper also extends the prior literature by focusing on the nexus between the CEO characteristics and

share price. Second, we contribute to the corporate governance literature by providing Nigerian evidence that the attributes of the CEO are associated with companies' share price. In this vein, our research responds to calls for a better understanding of the Nigerian infrastructure of CEOs, as previous attempts that examine the effects of CEO characteristics on share price have not reflected the current organizational pressures faced by firms. Third, we contribute to the share price literature by showing that the role of the CEO in improving a firm's share price cannot be ignored. The remaining sections consist of (i) literature review and hypotheses development, (ii) data and methodology, (iii) results and discussions, and (iv) conclusions and recommendations.

2. Literature review and hypothesis development

Agency theory explores the relationship between cooperative parties: a principal and their agent, to whom they delegate tasks. This relationship can be interpreted in two ways: (i) between the shareholders and managers, and (ii) between the creditors and the managers. So, agency theory comes into these frames to resolve the clash of interests arising from these three parties: shareholders, creditors and agents. Agency theory was developed by Jensen and Meckling in 1976. They concluded that the governance of a firm is based on how these tripartite interests are resolved, amicably.

Institutional theory is a theory on the deeper and more resilient aspects of social structure. Institutional theory refers to a theory about the ways in which organizational structures, norms, practices, and patterns of social relationships are connected to broader social and cultural environment. Institutional theory considers the processes by which structures, including schemes, rules, norms, and routines, become established as authoritative guidelines. Furthermore, institutional theorists assert that the institutional environment can strongly influence the development of formal structures in an organization. Therefore, a firm financial performance is not influenced by its CEO but also be several firm-specific characteristics. Thus, this paper considers other firm-specific variables as control variables, such as leverage, listing age, size, and growth.

Signaling theory is useful for describing behaviour when parties (individuals or organizations) have access to different information. Signaling theory suggests mechanisms for the transfer of information to another party with the target to resolve information asymmetries (Spence, 1973). The theory of signaling was developed by Michael Spence. It is interpreted that firms' financial performance sends signals to the market place that assist it in judging the quality of the financial information, it receives from firms. However, it must be noted that, this financial performance is partly the results of several factors, including CEO effectiveness. Therefore, the role of the CEO in a firm's share price cannot be ignored.

Furthermore, based on the three theories examined, the analytical framework for this study is explained by them. Both theories are the most popularly used theories to explain the behavioural changes in share price. In recognition of these three theories, the analytical framework of this paper is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Analytical Framework
Source: Authors (2023)

The schematic illustration depicted in Figure 1 shows the framework for this study. It illustrates the interaction with the dependent variable (share price) and the independent variable, CEO (proxied with CEO characteristics, which include, duality, nationality, gender, tenure, turnover, and ownership), including the control variables (leverage, listing age, firm size, and firm growth). The analytical framework in Figure 1 leads to further articulation of the model specification in methodology section. An effective CEO may hold also the position of the Chairman of the board of directors. Note that in Nigeria, the Central Bank of Nigeria has stopped banks from combining the two positions in the same person. Thus, duality is measured as a dummy where "1" is assigned to companies that have a CEO that is separated from the chairman and "0" for otherwise. Furthermore, CEO nationality is measured as dummy where

"1" is assigned for companies that have foreign CEOs and "0" for otherwise. In the same vein, CEO gender is measured as dummy where "1" is assigned to companies that have female CEOs and "0" for otherwise. CEO tenure is measured as dummy where "1" is assigned to companies that have CEOs that have stay for 3 years and "0" for CEOs with less than 3 years tenure. Furthermore, CEO turnover is measured as dummy where "1" is assigned to companies that have a change of CEOs in a particular year and "0" for otherwise. Finally, CEO ownership is measured as number of CEO shares divided by total numbers of shares (%). On the control variables, leverage is measured as total liabilities divided by total asset. Firm listing is measured as number of years a company is trading in the stock exchange. Firm size is measured as natural log of total asset. Firm growth is measured as current year revenue minus previous year revenue divided by previous revenue (%).

Prior studies on the role of CEO in improving share price have determined that effective CEO is associated with companies' share price (Al-Mamun et al., 2020; Braun & Sharma, 2007; Brickley, 2003; Bryan et al., 2000; Chang et al., 2006; Gilson & Vetsuypens, 1993; Harper et al., 2019; Hill & Phan, 2017; Lehn & Makhija, 1997; Mulyati et al., 2021; Neifar & Ajilli, 2019; Ozkan, 2011; Shivdasani & Yermack, 1999; Sholichah et al., 2021; Withisuphakorn & Jiraporn, 2015). However, only a few studies examine the effect of CEO characteristics on a firm's share price.

For instance, Dahya et al. (1996) investigate whether the stock market prefers companies to award the positions of chairman and chief executive officer to two different people instead of permitting a single individual, the 'dual CEO', to combine them. The results suggest (a) that the market responds favourably to the separation of the two roles and unfavourably to their fusion and (b) that the market performance (share price) of companies which adopt a 'dual CEO' appears to decline subsequent to this change.

Furthermore, Dherment-Ferere and Renneboog (2000) analyse the share price reactions to changes in CEO. The results show that an announcement of a forced CEO resignation is hailed favourably by the share price with a small but significantly positive increase of 0.5%. In addition, Dedman and Lin (2002) examine share price behaviour surrounding announcements of CEO departures from UK firms listed on the All Share Index between 1990 and 1995. They find that many firms choose not to announce CEO departures, and that these firms have poorer market performance records, and higher chances of future failure, than those firms who officially announce CEO turnover to the London Stock Exchange.

Braun and Sharma (2007) empirically examine the relationship between CEO duality and stock price performance in family-controlled public firms. They find that duality by itself does not influence stock price performance. Furthermore, Lilienfeld-Toal and Ruenza (2014) examine the relationship between CEO ownership and stock price performance. The effect was stronger, suggesting that CEO ownership can reverse the negative impact of weak governance. Also,

owner-CEOs are value increasing: they reduce empire building and run their firms more efficiently.

Furthermore, Olsen et al. (2014) investigate the relationship between CEOs of *Fortune* 500 companies and stock valuation. Using panel data from 1992 through 2009, they show that firms' share price increased higher. Withisuphakorn and Jiraporn (2015) explore how powerful CEOs influence the extent of stock price informativeness. Using idiosyncratic volatility to measure stock price informativeness, they find that firms with more powerful CEOs experience a higher share price.

Also, Hill and Phan (2017) examine the relationship between CEO tenure and stock price and conclude that the association is inverse. Neifar and Ajilli (2019) examine the influence of CEO characteristics on stock price synchronicity (SPS) of German companies and CEO tenure was found to have impact on SPS. Using the GLS regression, they find that CEO tenure affects positively SPS.

Furthermore, Harper et al. (2019) examine the impact of CEO power on stock price. Using a large panel sample with 17,816 firm-year observations, they find a significant negative impact of CEO power on stock price. Also, Mamun et al. (2020) find that powerful chief executive officers (CEOs) are associated with higher stock prices. Mulyati et al. (2021) examine empirically the effect of CEO tenure on stock prices using data from 77 firms, covering 2013-2017 observation period. The results show that CEO tenure has influence on stock prices. Furthermore, the Association of Executive Search and Leadership Consultants (2023) examines the effects of CEO on stock prices following more than 900 public firms. The value of stocks of the firm increased by an average of 5.3%. The impact was even greater when the CEO is adjudged by the board as effective (9.3% increase). Based these mix results, the following hypotheses are proposed:

- H₁: CEO duality has no significant impact on share price.
- H₂: CEO nationality has no significant impact on share price.
- H₃: CEO gender has no significant impact on share price.
- H₄: CEO tenure has no significant impact on share price.
- H₅: CEO turnover has no significant impact on share price.
- H₆: CEO ownership has no significant impact on share price.

The remaining part of this paper covers data and methodology, results and discussions, and conclusions and recommendations.

3. Data and Methodology

Our sample consists of 134 companies that are on the Main Board of the Nigerian Exchange from 2008 to 2022. We collected financial data from the Nigerian Exchange website. After

merging the datasets, we have 2,010 observations (134 firms, 15 years). The model of the study is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 SP_{i,t} = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 DUAL_{i,t} + \beta_2 NATI_{i,t} \\
 & + \beta_3 GEND_{i,t} + \beta_4 TENU_{i,t} + \beta_5 TURN_{i,t} \\
 & + \beta_6 OWNE_{i,t} + \beta_7 LEV_{i,t} + \beta_8 LAGE_{i,t} + \beta_9 FS_{i,t} + \beta_{10} FG_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t}
 \end{aligned}$$

Whereas, SP is share price, DUAL is CEO duality, GEND is CEO gender, TENU is CEO tenure, TURN is CEO turnover, OWNE is CEO ownership, LEV is firm leverage, LAGE is firm listing age, FS is firm size, and FG is firm growth.

In the model, the dependent variable is the share price, based on the rule of averaging, being the average of share price at the beginning and at the end of the fiscal year. Details of the measurement of all the variables are provided in Table 1 as follows.

Table 1. *Measurement of variables*

Serial	Variable	Measurement	A prior expectation
1	Y, Share price	Average of share price at the beginning and at the end of year t for firm i	
2	X ₁ , CEO Duality	Measured as a dummy where "1" is assigned to companies that have a CEO that is separated from the chairman and "0" for otherwise.	-
3	X ₂ , CEO Nationality	Measured as dummy where "1" is assigned for companies that have foreign CEOs and "0" for otherwise.	+
4	X ₃ , CEO Gender	Measured as dummy where "1" is assigned to companies that have female CEOs and "0" for otherwise.	+
5	X ₄ , CEO Tenure	Measured as dummy where "1" is assigned to companies that have CEOs that have stay for 3 years and "0" for CEOs with less than 3 years tenure.	+/-
6	X ₅ , CEO Turnover	Measured as dummy where "1" is assigned to companies that have a change of CEOs in a particular year and "0" for otherwise.	+/-
7	X ₆ , CEO Ownership	Measured as number of CEO shares divided by total numbers of shares (%).	+
8	X ₇ , LEV, Leverage	Measured as total liabilities divided by total asset.	+/-
9	X ₈ , LAGE, Listing age	Measured as number of years a company is trading in the stock exchange.	+/-
10	X ₉ , FS, Firm size	Measured as natural log of total asset.	+/-
11	X ₁₀ , FG, Firm growth	Measured as current year revenue minus previous year revenue divided by previous revenue (%).	+

Source: Authors (2023)

Our a priori expectations are as follows:

X₁<0, a fusion of CEO and Chairman will lead to a fall in share price.

X₂>0, a foreign CEO will lead to a rise in share price.

X₃>0, a female CEO will lead to a rise in share price.

X₄<0, a prolonged CEO tenure will lead to a fall in share price.

X₅<0, a negative CEO turnover will lead to a fall in share price.

X₆<0, a CEO ownership will lead to a rise in share price.

The data sets are sourced from the annual reports and accounts of the sampled firms, through the Nigerian Exchange website (www.ngxgroup.com). Companies annual reports and accounts are known vehicles for communicating with stakeholders. They represent official channels of communication between the sampled firms and stakeholders. Though, they are *ex post facto*, they represent figures of facts that had happened to the firms. A number of scholars have also used financial statements. According to Gary et al. (2011), financial statements are official channels of communications used by the firm to reach members of the public. STATA 15.1 is used to analyse the data.

The data is panel and the dependent variable (share price) is limitless, therefore, the method of analysis is the Generalized Method of Moments (GMM). The choice of method of analysis is informed that GMM offers advantage over (i) cross-sectional and time series data, (ii) it controls both within and between endogeneity in panel data set, and (iii) there is no need to conduct diagnostic tests of normality and heteroskedasticity of residuals, multicollinearity, linearity, which are associated with Pooled Ordinary Least Squares Model, because it overcomes these challenges (Baum et al., 2007; Brooks & Gelman, 1998; Buchinsky, 1998; Caselli et al., 1996; Chan et al., 1992; Hansen, 1982; Hayden & O'Connell, 1975; Newey & West, 1987; Stock et al., 2002; Zivot & Wang, 2006).

4. Results and Discussions

Table 2 presents the descriptive statistics for all variables, which covers the number of observations, central mean, standard deviation, minimum mean and maximum mean.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
SP	2010	10.508	10.339	.5	47.95
DUAL	2010	.919	.274	0	1
NATI	2010	.263	.441	0	1
GEND	2010	.019	.136	0	1
TENU	2010	.681	.467	0	1
TURN	2010	.194	.396	0	1
OWNE	2010	2.551	6.772	0	25.081
LEV	2010	.762	.22	.315	2.478
LAGE	2010	26.9	11.901	2	48
FSIZE	2010	7.653	.509	5.97	9.03
GROWTH	2010	25.814	22.332	0	99.44

Source: STATA 15.1 Outputs

As indicated by the results in Table 2, the number of observations is 2,010 (134 firms, multiplied by 15 years). Furthermore, the average of share price is ₦10.508, the average of CEO duality is .919, the average of CEO nationality is .263, the average of CEO gender is .019 (1.9 percent), the average of CEO tenure is .681, the average of CEO turnover is .194, and the average of CEO ownership is 2.551 percent. On control variables, the average of leverage is 76.2 percent, the average of listing age is 27 years, the average of firm size is 7.653 times, and the average of firm growth is 25.814 percent.

Furthermore, the standard deviation of share price is ₦10.339, which is extremely close to the mean, implying that the volatility of share price is high enough to warrant this study, the standard deviation of CEO duality is .274, the standard deviation of CEO nationality is .441, the standard deviation of CEO gender is .136 (13.6 percent), the standard deviation of CEO tenure is .467, the standard deviation of CEO turnover is .396, the standard deviation of CEO ownership is 6.772 percent. On control variables, the standard deviation of leverage is 22 percent, the standard deviation of listing age is 12 years, the standard deviation of firm size is .509 times, and the standard deviation of firm growth is 22.332 percent.

Also, the minimum mean of share price is ₦.5, the minimum mean of CEO duality is 0, the minimum mean of CEO nationality is 0, the minimum mean of CEO gender is 0 (0 percent), the minimum mean of CEO tenure is 0, the minimum mean of CEO turnover is 0, the minimum mean of CEO ownership is 0 percent. On control variables, the minimum mean of leverage is 31.5 percent, the minimum mean of listing age is 2 years, the minimum mean of firm size is 5.97 times, and the minimum mean of firm growth is 0 percent.

Furthermore, the maximum mean of share price is ₦47.95, the maximum mean of CEO duality is 1, the maximum mean of CEO nationality is 1, the maximum mean of CEO gender is 1 (100 percent), the maximum mean of CEO tenure is 1, the maximum mean of CEO turnover is 1, the maximum mean of CEO ownership is 25.081 percent. On control variables, the maximum mean of leverage is 247.8 percent, the maximum mean of listing age is 48 years, the maximum mean of firm size is 9.03 times, and the maximum mean of firm growth is 99.44 percent. One major highlight from the findings in Table 2 is that the dependent variable, share price deserves to be investigated (researched) as it is the case in this paper because the spread or volatility from the mean is too high. While the mean is 10.508, the standard deviation is 10.339, which suggests that the percentage of variability is 98.39 (10.339/10.508) percent. Among the independent variable's proxies to be watched carefully are CEO nationality, gender, tenure, turnover, and ownership. On the control variables to be watched carefully by managers are leverage and firm growth. The variability or volatility in these variables are too high to be comfortable.

Furthermore, the Pearson correlation coefficient matrix is used to identify the direction and strength of the relationship between the CEO characteristics (duality, nationality, gender, tenure,

turnover, and ownership), on the one hand, control variables (leverage, firm listing age, firm size, and firm growth) and share price (average of share price at the beginning and at the end). The results are reported in Table 3.

Table 3. Pearson correlation matrix

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)
(1) SP	1.000										
(2) DUAL	0.033 (0.675)	1.000									
(3) NATI	-0.202* (0.011)	0.177* (0.025)	1.000								
(4) GEND	-0.082 (0.302)	0.041 (0.606)	-0.082 (0.300)	1.000							
(5) TENU	0.119 (0.135)	-0.007 (0.929)	-0.049 (0.537)	-0.202* (0.010)	1.000						
(6) TURN	-0.048 (0.550)	0.146 (0.066)	0.031 (0.697)	0.282* (0.000)	-0.649* (0.000)	1.000					
(7) OWNE	0.272* (0.001)	0.112 (0.158)	-0.225* (0.004)	-0.052 (0.512)	0.229* (0.004)	-0.167* (0.035)	1.000				
(8) LEV	0.170* (0.032)	-0.102 (0.198)	-0.135 (0.089)	0.044 (0.584)	-0.020 (0.803)	0.021 (0.790)	0.368* (0.000)	1.000			
(9) LAGE	-0.115 (0.148)	-0.118 (0.137)	-0.057 (0.472)	0.059 (0.455)	0.130 (0.102)	-0.142 (0.072)	0.055 (0.493)	-0.065 (0.417)	1.000		
(10) FSIZE	-0.240* (0.002)	0.141 (0.074)	-0.035 (0.660)	0.175* (0.027)	0.045 (0.576)	-0.006 (0.938)	-0.089 (0.261)	-0.076 (0.338)	0.389* (0.000)	1.000	
(11) GROWTH	0.075 (0.347)	-0.089 (0.262)	0.012 (0.884)	-0.058 (0.469)	0.141 (0.076)	-0.099 (0.211)	0.116 (0.143)	-0.013 (0.866)	-0.058 (0.467)	-0.026 (0.745)	1.000

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Source: STATA 15.1 Outputs

As indicated by the results in Table 3, CEO duality is positively correlated with share price, though not significant. Our a priori expectation is that CEO duality will cause a fall in share price. Also, CEO nationality is negatively significant with share price. Our a priori expectation is that CEO nationality will be significant with share price but we thought that it will bring a positive correlation. CEO gender is negatively correlated with share price, though it is not significant. Our a priori expectation is that CEO gender will bring in significant positive correlation since women directors are known to have the discipline required to earn positive financial performance, which signals into high share price. CEO tenure is positively correlated with share price, which is in contrast with our a priori expectation. We had expected that the longer a CEO stays, the fall in share price. CEO turnover is negatively correlated with share price, though not significant. We expect that a negative CEO turnover will bring down the share price of the firm, however, we are expecting the results to be significant. CEO ownership of equity shares is significantly and positively correlated with share price. These results are consistent with our *ex-ante* expectations.

Based on all known theories of motivation, we expect that the CEO share ownership will motivate the CEO to deliver on high financial performance, which can signal into high share price. On the control variables, leverage is significantly and positively correlated with share price. We expect leverage to be significant but with negative impact. Firm listing age is negatively correlated with share price, however, it is not significant. This is consistent with our a priori expectations. Firm size is significantly and negatively correlated with share price. This is consistent with our a priori expectations. Finally, firm growth is positively correlated with share price but it is not significant.

Furthermore, the GMM regression results for the model are given in Table 4.

Table 4. GMM Regression Results

Number of parameters = 11

Number of moments = 11

Initial weight matrix: Unadjusted

Number of obs = 2,010

GMM weight matrix: Robust

	Coef.	Robust Std. Err.	z	P>z	[95% Conf. Interval]
DUAL	3.189595	2.060683	1.55	0.122	-0.84927 7.22846
NATI	-4.266928	1.76092	-2.42	0.015	-7.718268 -.8155878
GEND	-3.45979	1.81477	-1.91	0.057	-7.016673 .0970942
TENU	2.42374	1.643356	1.47	0.140	-0.7971783 5.644658
TURN	1.332309	2.132508	0.62	0.532	-2.84733 5.511948
OWNE	.2252714	.1373577	1.64	0.101	-0.0439447 .4944874
LEV	3.96466	4.316923	0.92	0.358	-4.496353 12.42567
LAGE	-.0291182	.0641219	-0.45	0.650	-0.1547948 .0965584
FSIZE	-4.487036	1.634551	-2.75	0.006	-7.690698 -1.283374
GROWTH	.0221744	.0346198	0.64	0.522	-0.0456792 .0900279
/b0	37.80697	11.9183	3.17	0.002	14.44753 61.16641

Source: STATA 15.1 Outputs

The coefficients of CEO nationality, gender, and firm size are statistically significant at the level of 0.05, 0.10 and 0.01, respectively. The three proxies of the independent variable affect the dependent variable in the same direction. In contrast, CEO duality, tenure, turnover, and ownership, leverage, listing age and firm growth are not significant. These results are mixed, that is, some are consistent with our a priori expectations and others are not. It should be noted that these results are robust results. Overall, our findings indicate that the market does not correctly price the incentive effects of CEO duality, tenure, turnover, ownership, and leverage, firm listing age and firm growth.

In this study, we expand share price performance research by investigating the effects of CEO characteristics commonly associated with CEO effectiveness and the combined effect of this effectiveness in which firms exist to maximize share price performance. Overall, we find evidence of significant effects from CEO nationality, CEO gender, and firm size. However, the

paper failed to find similar significant effects of CEO duality, tenure, turnover and ownership, leverage, firm listing age and firm growth on share price performance.

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

Share price performance is important consideration for investment decisions. Through it, a firm can improve and attract investors, both potential and existing. While prior research has indicated that share price performance is central to attract investments, studies addressing such have mainly focused on the determinants of share price performance rather than on the effects of the CEO. Our first set of results fills this gap, providing evidence that the attributes of the CEOs that reflect their effectiveness are associated with the share price performance, extending the literature on share price performance. CEO nationality, CEO gender and firm size are determinants of share price performance. While CEO duality, tenure, turnover, ownership, leverage, firm listing age and firm growth are not determinants of share price performance in Nigeria's 134 listed firms on the Main Board of the Nigerian Exchange. We recommend that firms should consider the engagement of a foreign CEO, particularly in industry, in which the local economy has not developed a cream of CEOs. Furthermore, we recommend the consideration of women in the appointment of CEOs. Also, we recommend that future research should consider dividing the sample firms based on their size, since in this study, firm size is significant. Future research should consider increasing the sample size. Also, future research should expand CEO characteristics to include CEO age, CEO education, CEO overconfidence, CEO pay, and other CEO characteristics that may affect share price performance.

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